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A Creative Folio

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Nursing Research: A Journey of Growth, Courage and Cheer!

I started as a student, research I did despise,
But as a course requirement, I had to realize.
In the classroom, our teacher guided each part,
Teaching the basics, igniting a start.

From knowing what research is, its types and its ways,
To writing introductions that brighten the days.
Reviewing the literature, methods to prepare,
Proposal approved new burdens to bear.

Sleepless nights followed, deadlines to meet,
Missing occasions, yet refusing defeat.
But once the defense was finally done,
True happiness bloomed, fulfillment was won.

As graduates, nurses with futures ahead,
Postgraduate dreams in our hearts are spread.
Master's or doctorate, the cycle repeats,
Research returns, with new goals to meet.

Though once avoided, now cherished with pride,
Nursing Research walks with us side by side.
A subject of struggle, yet love it became,
An enduring journey, with honor and name.